

The Geopolitical Transformation of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic: From the Zangezur Corridor to the Trump Route

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Abstract

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Nakhchivan holds strategic importance worldwide due to its history, cultural heritage, and geopolitical significance. Having come under the rule of many states throughout history, Nakhchivan gained autonomous status under the Moscow Treaty signed in March 1921, and the Kars Treaty confirmed this status, signed in October of the same year. Although Turkey's contact with the region was minimal during the Soviet era, the legal status of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Region became clear after the Soviet Union's collapse and Azerbaijan's declaration of independence. According to the Constitution of Azerbaijan, the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is free in its internal affairs but subordinate to the Republic of Azerbaijan in matters of foreign policy and defense. However, the First Karabakh War in the 1990s and Armenian attacks on Nakhchivan threatened peace and stability in the region. The first step towards ending the unrest and chaos in the region was only taken in 2020, following the 44-day Patriotic War. As a result of this step, Karabakh was liberated from occupation, and the Zangezur Corridor, along with Nakhchivan, Turkey's gateway to Azerbaijan and thus to the Turkic world, became more meaningful. However, in August 2025, US President Trump brought Baku and Yerevan together in Washington and announced a peace declaration between the two countries, introducing the concept of the Trump Road to the literature. Indeed, this study focuses on the status and historical background of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, as well as the evolution from the Zangezur Corridor to the Trump Road.

Nahçıvan Özerk Cumhuriyeti'nin Jeopolitik Dönüşümü: Zengezur Koridoru'ndan Trump Rotası'na

Özet

Anahtar Kelimeler:

Nahçıvan Özerk
Cumhuriyeti,
Zengezur Koridoru,
Trump Rotası,
Jeopolitik Dönüşüm

Nahçıvan tarihi geçmişi, kültürel birikimi ve jeopolitiği ile yerküre üzerinde stratejik bir öneme sahiptir. Tarihsel seyir içerisinde pek çok devletin egemenliği altına giren Nahçıvan, 1921 yılının Mart ayında imzalanan Moskova Antlaşmasıyla özerk bir statüye sahip olmuş, aynı yılın Ekim ayında imzalanan Kars Antlaşması ile de bu yapısı teyit edilmiştir. Her ne kadar Sovyet Sosyalist Cumhuriyetler Birliği (SSCB) döneminde Türkiye'nin bölge ile olan irtibatı asgari seviyeye inse de, SSCB'nin dağılmasına müteakip Azerbaycan'ın bağımsızlığını ilan etmesi ile birlikte Nahçıvan Özerk Bölgesi'nin hukuki pozisyonu netleşmiştir. Azerbaycan Anayasası'na göre Nahçıvan Özerk Cumhuriyeti, iç işlerinde serbest, dış politika ve savunma konularında ise Azerbaycan Cumhuriyeti'ne bağlı olmuştur. Ancak 1990'lı yıllarda yaşanan I. Karabağ Savaşı ve Ermenilerin Nahçıvan'a yönelik saldırıları bölgedeki barışı ve huzuru tehdit etmiştir. Bölgede yaşanan huzursuzlukların ve karmaşanın sona erdirilmesi için ilk adım ancak 2020 yılında 44 gün süren Vatan Muharebesi sonucunda atılabilmektedir. Bu adım neticesinde Karabağ işgalden azat edilmiş, Türkiye'nin Azerbaycan'a ve dolayısıyla Türk dünyasına açılan kapısı Nahçıvan ile birlikte Zengezur Koridoru daha anlamlı bir hale gelmiştir. Ancak 2025 yılının Ağustos ayına gelindiğinde ABD Başkanı Trump'ın Bakü'yü ve Erivan'ı Vaşington'da bir araya getirerek iki ülke arasında barışın ilan edildiğini duyurması Trump Rotası kavramını literatüre dahil etmiştir. Nitekim bu çalışmada Nahçıvan Özerk Cumhuriyeti'nin statüsü ve tarihsel geçmişi ile birlikte Zengezur Koridoru'ndan Trump Rotası'na evrilişin serencamı üzerinde durulmuştur.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic occupies a strategic position due to its geographical location. Having come under the sovereignty of many states throughout history, Nakhchivan gained autonomous status with the Moscow Treaty signed in March 1921, and this status was confirmed with the Kars Treaty signed in October of the same year. Although Turkey's contact with the region was minimal during the Soviet era, the legal status of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Region became clear after the Soviet Union's collapse and Azerbaijan's declaration of independence. According to the Constitution of Azerbaijan, the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is free in its internal affairs but subordinate to the Republic of Azerbaijan in matters of foreign policy and defense. However, the First Karabakh War in the 1990s and Armenian attacks on Nakhchivan threatened peace and stability in the region. This unrest and insecurity could only be resolved in 2020. The cooperation between Turkey and Azerbaijan in the arms and defense industry and their long-standing relationship have borne fruit. The territories that had been under Armenian occupation for years were liberated after the 44-day Patriotic War. The military success in the Patriotic War was also preserved at the negotiating table, and Karabakh gained its freedom. The liberation of Karabakh has made the Zangezur Corridor, along with Nakhchivan, Turkey's gateway to Azerbaijan and, thus, to the Turkic world.

The agreement signed in Moscow after the Patriotic War included a provision for a direct land connection between Azerbaijan and Nakhchivan. This provision required urgent steps to open and activate the Zangezur Corridor. However, the requirements of this agreement, brokered by Russia, have not been implemented, and the process has begun to drag on. In particular, Russia's decision to put its interests in the region on the back burner due to the war in Ukraine, as well as the bloodshed in Syria and Libya, among other places, has facilitated the United States' entry into the region. These lands, which have been home to many civilizations to date, have become the focal point of regional developments in the current period; they have been at the center of projects and approaches claimed to contribute to regional and global peace. US President Donald Trump's apparent desire and ambition to be remembered as the person who established peace in the world ended when he brought Azerbaijan and Armenia to the table. On August 8, 2025, US President Donald Trump brought together Azerbaijani President Ilham Aliyev and Armenian Prime Minister Nikol Pashinyan in Washington, DC, announcing that he had established peace between Azerbaijan and Armenia, which was seen as a striking development. Moreover, Trump's announcement of this peace initiative to the world as the Trump Route for International Peace and Prosperity (TRIPP) has led to the Zangezur Corridor, which has long been discussed, being renamed the Trump Route.

All these developments have led to a shift in the balance of power in the South Caucasus. The wars that have erupted have not only determined who controls the territories but have also made regional transportation and connectivity projects a matter of great importance. In this context, discussions on the Zangezur Corridor have brought to the fore the integration of Nakhchivan and Turkey into the Turkic World. However, Russia's relinquishment of its influence in the region to the US and Trump's plan to deploy US companies there have made it necessary to consider a new route known as the Trump Route. From the perspective of the Trump Route, the new situation has entered a phase in which regional geopolitics is being redefined. Indeed, this study highlights that the status and historical background of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic are not only a historical legacy but also a key factor in the region, focusing on the evolution from the Zangezur Corridor to the Trump Route.

2. THE HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT AND FORMATION OF NAKHCHIVAN'S STRATEGIC IDENTITY

Nahçıvan, whose history dates back centuries before the Common Era, has been under the rule of many states, including Manna, Med, Macedonia, Persia, Atropatene, and Rome. Nahçıvan, which fell under Sassanid rule in the third century AD, has been under the rule of states such as the Roman Empire, the Eastern Roman Empire, the Abbasids, the Seljuks, and the Golden Horde until the present day (Karamanlı, 2006: 294-295). The Nahçıvan Sanjak, which remained under the administration of the Ottoman Empire between 1724 and 1735, came to an end in October 1735 with the occupation of Nahçıvan by the Iranian army (Bilge, 2017: 70). Nahçıvan, which broke free from Iranian influence in 1747 and continued as an independent khanate, came under Russian rule following the Treaty of Turkmenchay, signed as a result of the Russo-Iranian War of 1826-1828 (Bektaş, 2023: 268). Nakhchivan, an autonomous republic within Azerbaijan, has long been a focal point due to its strategic location and ancient history, having served as a battleground for various civilizations. Nahçıvan, which holds a key position between Anatolia, Central Asia, and Southeast Asia, has been named "The

Gate of the East” by the Turks because of its location. As Nahçıvan is the gateway to other Turkic republics from Turkey, it is of great geopolitical and geostrategic importance for the Turkic World (Şimşek, 2010: 111). At the same time, since these lands were once part of the Ottoman Empire and later part of the Qajar Dynasty, they share the common heritage of the great Turkish dynasties established in the region (Topsakal, 2020).

In 1920, following the Ankara Government's signing of the Treaty of Kars with Armenia, the regions of Iğdır and Kars, which had been under Armenian occupation since 1918, were regained. The regions of Nakhchivan, Shahtahı, and Şarut were also placed under Turkish protection, and it was stipulated that Armenia could not interfere in these territories. However, the Moscow Treaty signed between the Government of the Grand National Assembly of Turkey and Soviet Russia on March 16, 1921, determined Turkey's current borders. While Kars and Ardahan remained in Turkey, Batum was left outside Turkey's borders. At the same time, the Moscow Treaty was recorded as an agreement that also determined the status of Nakhchivan. Under this agreement, no referendum was envisaged for Nakhchivan, and it was decided that it would be an autonomous republic under Azerbaijan's protection, with the stipulation that it would never be ceded to a third state (Soysal, 1983). The status of Nakhchivan was confirmed by the Treaty of Kars signed on October 13, 1921. By 1991, after Azerbaijan declared its independence, Nakhchivan retained its status as an “autonomous republic” within Azerbaijan and became the only land border between Turkey and Azerbaijan, with a border length of approximately 18 kilometers. On the other hand, the fact that Azerbaijanis could access Nakhchivan only via Iran or by air hindered Nakhchivan's development (Rehimov, 2023).

However, the liberation of Shusha, Fuzuli, Jabrayıl, Zangilan, Kubadlı, Khojalı, Khojavend, and many other Azerbaijani territories that had been under Armenian occupation for years following the 44-day Patriotic War (Second Karabakh War) has strengthened Azerbaijan's hand. Azerbaijan's military victory directly influenced the inclusion of a clause in the Moscow agreement that opened a transport corridor between Azerbaijan's mainland and Nakhchivan. With the agreement signed in Moscow, Karabakh was liberated from occupation, and the corridor that will open with Nakhchivan, Turkey's gateway to Azerbaijan and, consequently, to the Turkic world, has become more meaningful (Rehimov, 2023). At this point, if the Zangezur Corridor is opened, Nakhchivan will become a central transit and diplomatic hub not only for Turkey but also for the Organization of Turkic States. This situation will further strengthen Nakhchivan's autonomous structure while making Turkey's influence in the Caucasus permanent (Yüce & Azizova, 2024: 32-34). Indeed, this agreement, signed in Moscow, coupled with Russia's exhaustion due to the war in Ukraine and the failure to take the necessary steps to implement the relevant corridor, has prompted global and regional actors to take action in this area. In particular, Trump's desire to win the Nobel Peace Prize and his efforts to become a champion of peace, coupled with the US's desire to fill the emerging power vacuum politically and the goal of American companies to enter the region and increase their activities, have led to the implementation of the Trump Route, which we will discuss in the following sections.

In this regard, the geostrategic position of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic in the South Caucasus plays a decisive role not only for Azerbaijan but also in shaping the balance of power between Turkey, Iran, and Armenia. The fact that Nakhchivan is separated from the main territory of Azerbaijan by Armenian territory gives Nakhchivan both a fragile and strategic character. Nahçıvan's geopolitical position, on the one hand, exposes the region to security risks. On the other hand, it transforms it into an indispensable transit hub for energy transmission lines, transportation corridors, and transit routes (Kocalar, 2025: 8-17). Turkey's border with Nakhchivan, in particular, serves as a gateway for Turkey to both the East and the Turkic world. For this reason, countries seeking to establish influence in the region cannot afford to ignore Turkey.

Indeed, Nakhchivan's geographical features, historical background, and geopolitics make it strategically important. Transportation routes in the South Caucasus are being reshaped, and regional projects are being planned. While all this is happening, the geopolitics and political position of Nakhchivan, which remains an autonomous republic affiliated with Azerbaijan, play an important role in the regional security equation. The strategic importance of Nakhchivan is increasingly understood, and foreign policy steps by states are being shaped within this framework (Erdei & Gally, 2023: 133-139).

3. THE HISTORICAL BACKGROUND AND GEOPOLITICAL IMPORTANCE OF THE ZANGEZUR CORRIDOR

Zengezur, named after the Zengene people of the Kayı tribe, one of the 24 Oğuz tribes, is an ancient land of Azerbaijan. These ancient lands, which have been under various states' rule for centuries, have mostly remained under Turkish rule and have always retained their strategic importance. The turning points in Zengezur's history

were the Treaty of Gulistan, signed on September 12, 1813, and the Treaty of Turkmenchay, signed on February 10, 1828. As a result of these treaties, 1,300 of the 8,249 Armenian families from Iran were settled in Karabakh and Zengezur, marking the beginning of a difficult process that continues to this day (Gelir & Saygılı, 2024: 2057). The region in southern Armenia, referred to as Syunik by Armenians, is called Zengezur by Azerbaijanis. To the south of this region lies Iran, to the east lies Azerbaijan, and to the west lies the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, which is part of Azerbaijan (bbc.com, 2022). The Zengezur Corridor holds geostrategic importance in the South Caucasus region. This corridor is a transit route connecting the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic with the mainland. However, with the outbreak of the Nagorno-Karabakh War in the 1990s, Nakhchivan became isolated from mainland Azerbaijan, severing the connection between them. Re-establishing this severed link and reconnecting Nakhchivan to the mainland will be possible with the opening of the Zengezur Corridor. At the same time, the opening of the Zengezur Corridor will resolve many issues, primarily regional trade and energy transfer. These developments will contribute to both regional development and regional peace (Maden, 2023).

The successful implementation of the Zengezur Corridor will undoubtedly make significant contributions to the geopolitics of the South Caucasus. The Corridor will connect the territories of Nakhchivan and Azerbaijan, and will activate land and rail routes between Turkey, Azerbaijan, and other Turkic republics. Moreover, the historic Silk Road will be revived, and China's "One Belt, One Road" project will gain momentum in terms of regional cooperation and trade (aa.com.tr, 2021). The Zengezur Corridor is a strategic passage in the heart of the South Caucasus that could directly connect Turkey and Azerbaijan by land. Historically, this route, which the USSR left within Armenia's borders in the 1920s, has physically separated the Turkic world in the region. The ceding of Zengezur to Armenia has been described as a strategic move by Russia (Kızıllı, 2016: 4-5). The corridor, which came to the fore with the tripartite declaration signed after the 2020 Karabakh War, is important both for bridging a historical divide and for establishing new geopolitical ties. The agreement ending the war among Russia, Azerbaijan, and Armenia, signed in Moscow on November 10, 2020, has helped shift the regional balance of power (Avan, 2025: 75).

Currently, there are no natural gas or oil reserves in the Zengezur Corridor. What makes this corridor geopolitically prominent and increases its strategic importance is that it will diversify Europe's energy demand security. In addition, transporting the rich natural gas and oil reserves of the Turkic Republics in the Turkistan region through a reliable country with regional and global influence, such as Turkey, further increases the strategic importance of the Corridor. Finally, the Zengezur Corridor could significantly shorten existing trade routes and provide an alternative, safer option for energy transmission lines affected by regional instability, thereby increasing its strategic importance. In this context, the Corridor will not only contribute to faster, more cost-effective implementation of commercial transportation processes but also offer an important geopolitical advantage by strengthening energy supply security and increasing route diversity in energy transfer. In this regard, the Zengezur Corridor is considered a critical link that supports regional economic integration and strengthens the South Caucasus's strategic position in international trade and energy networks (Özdemir, 2025: 227).

As a strategic route, the Zengezur Corridor encompasses the concepts of security and sovereignty in the South Caucasus. The corridor is extremely important in that it will connect Nakhchivan, which has no land border with Azerbaijan, to the motherland. In addition, the corridor will establish a direct land connection between Turkey and Azerbaijan, providing Turkey with direct/uninterrupted access to the Turkic world. Therefore, the Zengezur Corridor will serve as a bridge between Turkey, Azerbaijan, and Turkistan, both physically and symbolically, facilitating geopolitical integration with the Turkic world. This Corridor, which came to the agenda under the agreement signed in Moscow after the 44-day Patriotic War in 2020, has been seen as a critical project for re-establishing regional transportation networks and refining economic integration (Acicbe, 2020: 156-162). The implementation of the corridor will serve both Turkey's integration with Azerbaijan and the Turkic world and contribute to ensuring Azerbaijan's territorial integrity.

On the other hand, the geography known as the Zengezur Corridor stands out as a region where not only regional but also global power struggles take place. Although South Caucasus has been an area where many states have fought for dominance throughout history, it has particularly come to the fore as Russia's sphere of influence in the last century. Seeking to maintain its dominance and act as the protector of the South Caucasus, Russia has repeatedly demonstrated its desire to be an active player in the region, particularly in the areas of transportation and security. Similarly, Iran attaches importance to the region for its national security and closely monitors developments there against potential threats from the north. On the other hand, the US and European states also attach special importance to the region in terms of energy supply security and the diversification of

transportation networks in Eurasia. For this reason, the Zengezur Corridor comes to the fore not only in the context of transportation or energy supply security, but also as a geography where regional and global power balances are being reshaped (Huseynov, 2023: 63-71).

4. THE CHANGING GEOPOLITICAL BALANCE IN SOUTH CAUCASUS AFTER THE SECOND KARABAKH WAR

The Zengezur Corridor plays a strategic role in the context of restructuring regional transport routes. It is a critical transit point in ensuring the continuity of trade routes extending from China to Europe within the scope of the Middle Corridor. At the same time, it strengthens integration between Turkey, Azerbaijan, and Central Asian countries by enabling the planning of new pipelines, fiber networks, and logistics infrastructure in terms of energy policies (Yüce & Azizova, 2024: 25-27). In this context, the Zengezur Corridor and the broader geo-economic route known as the “Trump Route” aim to establish an uninterrupted logistics connection stretching from China and Central Asia across the Caspian Sea to Azerbaijan, then through Zengezur and Nakhchivan to Turkey, and ultimately to European markets. In this regard, the Second Karabakh War in 2020 was a historic turning point that fundamentally transformed the balance of power in the South Caucasus. The Karabakh issue, which had been a “frozen conflict” for nearly thirty years, has evolved into a new geopolitical phase with the outcome of the war in Azerbaijan's favor (Ateş & Kılıç, 2025: 31-42). The military success achieved in the 44-day Patriotic War not only liberated the territories occupied by Armenia but also redrew the balance of power in the region. During this period, Russia's dominance in the region was called into question, and the passive conflict zone in the South Caucasus turned into an active struggle. Subsequently, the realization that Russia could no longer maintain its dominance in the region led to US intervention.

Armenia's defeat in the war led to turmoil in its domestic politics, while Azerbaijan experienced justified pride at emerging victorious. After the war, regional balances shifted against Armenia and in favor of Azerbaijan. Azerbaijan gained diplomatic and military strength in the South Caucasus and, thanks to its relations with Turkey, managed to get what it wanted at the negotiating table. In particular, Turkey's declaration of open support for Azerbaijan during the war, along with its military and unmanned aerial vehicle support, demonstrated the solidification of the alliance between Turkey and Azerbaijan (Helvacıköylü, 2021: 161-169). Undoubtedly, Turkey's open military and diplomatic support for Azerbaijan has been the cornerstone of change in the region. During the war, Russia did not intervene in the conflict but contributed to the ceasefire by bringing Baku and Yerevan together in Moscow. Furthermore, Russia sought to establish military control over the region by deploying peacekeeping forces under the agreement. On the one hand, the region's importance to Turkey is evident; on the other, Russia's desire to avoid losing its influence there is clear. In addition to these countries, as transportation routes were being re-planned and the balance of power in the South Caucasus shifted, the United States also took steps to position itself within this equation. The South Caucasus has now become a competitive arena where transportation, energy, and trade take center stage, rather than armed conflict (Gafarlı, 2024, 153-164).

Indeed, the 44-day Patriotic War has changed all geopolitical balances in the South Caucasus. The region has now become multi-actor and dynamic. This geography, in the immediate vicinity or on the borders of Turkey, Azerbaijan, Iran, Russia, and Armenia, has become a point of intersection for global powers such as the US and China, which are also striving to establish influence in the region. The region's security, transportation projects, and other factors have evolved to the point that they cannot be considered independently of one another (Javadi, 2018: 19-28). These developments in the South Caucasus aim to establish a land connection between Turkey and Azerbaijan. Establishing this connection would involve integrating the Turkic world, laying energy lines, and facilitating commercial integration. Given the region's importance to Russia, it continues to strive to maintain its historical influence. Iran's approach to the region is based on the concern that movements could undermine its own territorial integrity (Köstem, 2021: 5-7). As can be seen, South Caucasus emerges as an arena where many states are engaged in a power struggle.

While all these developments were unfolding, US President Trump frequently made headlines with statements that changed the global agenda. In particular, on September 23, 2025, Trump declared at the United Nations General Assembly that he had ended seven wars. One of these seven wars was the war between Azerbaijan and Armenia. On August 8, 2025, a peace agreement was signed between Azerbaijan and Armenia in Washington under Trump's auspices, introducing the concept of the “Trump Route” into the literature (bbc.com.tr, 2025). This concept has gained visibility as a reality that will affect the geopolitics and economy of the entire South Caucasus, beyond just the two countries involved (Russia Matters, 2025). Indeed, the process stretching from

the Zangezur Corridor to the Trump Route has developed in this manner. Trump's involvement in this manner has shaped global power competition in the South Caucasus around the axes of the economy and transportation. Following the 44-day Patriotic War, with the tripartite declaration signed in Moscow, the Zengezur Corridor, which aimed to establish a land connection between Azerbaijan and the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, suddenly became the "Trump Route" with the intervention of the US under Trump's leadership, bringing logistics, economy, trade, and energy to the forefront. Trump's move has led to the emergence of a competitive arena encompassing China's Belt and Road Initiative, Russia's Eurasian vision, and Europe's energy security (Nan, 2025). In light of these assessments, the "Trump Route" perspective has redefined the geopolitical position of the South Caucasus within the global system.

5. NAKHCHIVAN'S FUTURE AND TRUMP THE NEW GEOPOLITICAL REALITY SHAPED BY HIS COURSE

The Zengezur Corridor project, which emerged from the agreement signed in Moscow after the Second Karabakh War, was of great importance to the Turkic world, particularly Turkey and Azerbaijan. This is because implementing the project would create a direct connection between Turkey and Azerbaijan, and Azerbaijan would be connected to the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic via land and rail transport from this region (bbc.com, 2022). The corridor was not only a physical transportation route but was also considered a cultural, economic, and political integration project connecting the Turkic world. In this context, implementing the corridor meant putting the regional cooperation goals outlined in the Organization of Turkic States' vision documents into practice. In the long term, it had the potential to deepen integration in areas such as the common market, energy security, and defense cooperation (Gençoğlu, 2024: 3-5). However, Moscow's inability or unwillingness to maintain the momentum that brought Baku and Yerevan together led the US to step in, causing the project, known as the Zangezur Corridor, to diverge both in name and substance.

U.S. President Donald Trump's "Road to Peace" declaration, announced on August 9, 2025, by bringing Aliyev and Pashinyan together in Washington, envisions the corridor being managed by an international consortium and the development of transportation and energy infrastructure along it. Given its strategic location, this corridor has the potential to serve as an alternative route for global trade and transportation networks. It also stands out as an important geopolitical line that could strengthen the land connection between the Central Asian Turkic Republics and the West in the post-Soviet era. In this regard, the corridor or route is expected to play a critical role in increasing regional connectivity, diversifying energy security, and reshaping the geopolitical balance in the South Caucasus (Özdemir, 2025: 222-223). At the heart of the framework put forward by Trump is a 43-kilometer strategic transit corridor called the Trump Route. These corridors will reopen borders that have been closed for a long time and will connect Turkey and Azerbaijan with the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic (Luciani, 2026: 1). This connection will initiate a structural transformation in Azerbaijan's economic and geopolitical position, in addition to its transportation and logistics policy. The geoeconomic axis, referred to as the "Trump Route," will become the fundamental tools for Azerbaijan's goal of transforming from a regional transit country into a strategic logistics hub on an Eurasian scale. This transformation signifies the conversion of political gains into geoeconomic advantage through concrete infrastructure investments, increased transport capacity, and regional integration, thereby reshaping connectivity in the South Caucasus (Mahmudov, 2026).

In essence, it is evident that all of US President Trump's actions at the global and regional levels have been shaped by the slogans "We Will Make America Great Again" and "America First." The US position in the South Caucasus goes beyond contributing to world peace; it is about US companies establishing dominance in the region and the US seeking a say in strategic transportation and energy routes. For this reason, this perspective, known as the Trump Route, beautifully explains the direction of US foreign policy (Önsay, 2017: 40-45). Indeed, there are important points that should not be overlooked at this stage. The declaration signed in Moscow meant that the Zangezur Corridor largely had a legal status outside Armenia's control, and that its security would be provided by Russia. However, with the Trump Route, emphasis is placed on Armenia's sovereignty, and the goal is for the corridor's security to be provided by Armenian security forces. According to the agreement made in Moscow, the corridor's operation was to be centered on Turkey, Azerbaijan, and Russia. Still, with the Trump Route, it is being transferred to a US-led consortium. With the Trump Route, Russia is losing its geopolitical power and being sidelined (Üren, 2025).

The operation of the Zangezur Corridor, known as the Trump Route, has been granted to the US for ninety-nine years. Roadways, railways, energy and pipeline networks, and digital fiber optic cables are planned to pass through the corridor. This situation has secured the US's entry into the region and led to a decline in the

activities of Russia and Iran. Turkey's strategic position as a regional power has become increasingly important (Uluyurt, 2025). However, it would be naive to view the route and framework presented by Trump solely as steps taken by the US to contribute to world peace. It is clear that Trump, who claims to contribute to world peace and to have ended many wars in this context, is not sincere. Some examples of this include his complicity in the genocide in Gaza by ignoring democratic values and international norms, his overthrow of the Venezuelan president in a midnight operation, and his declaration that he wanted to buy Greenland.

6. CONCLUSION

The Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, located at the center of the balance of power in the South Caucasus and prominent for its geopolitical position, is of extreme strategic importance to both regional and global actors. The status of Nakhchivan, determined by the Moscow Treaty and the Treaty of Kars signed in 1921, regained importance with Azerbaijan's independence and the collapse of the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics. Nakhchivan's strategic location has brought it to the forefront as an important actor in regional politics. Nahçıvan, which gained even greater importance with the Second Karabakh War between Azerbaijan and Armenia, has become the focal point of the Zangezur Corridor Project and the Trump Route Perspective. In particular, the prospect of meeting Europe's energy supply security needs, China's contribution to the Silk Road Project, and Turkey's ability to gain uninterrupted access to Azerbaijan and, consequently, the Turkic world, make Nakhchivan important from a geostrategic and geoeconomic perspective.

As can be seen, the importance of Nakhchivan and its related corridor, which has emerged as a strategic line, is increasing day by day and is on the agenda of global actors. Given its importance, Moscow's move was unsuccessful, but with Trump's intervention, it took on new dimensions and was presented to the public as a successful move (!). This step taken by the US under Trump's leadership did not manifest itself as direct military intervention in the region, but rather took the form of diplomatic efforts and strategic steps. This process, planned for implementation in the near future, is being closely monitored not only by the US but also by countries in the region. It should not be forgotten that the strong relationship between Turkey and Azerbaijan will continue to play a decisive role in the geopolitics of the South Caucasus. Although the demands and requests of the US, which is thousands of kilometers away from the region, or Russia, whose influence in the region is under threat, are written on paper, they will not last forever, given the fragility of the region and the existence of a strong relationship between Turkey and Azerbaijan. Similarly, the agreement reached in Moscow in 2020 has not been implemented, even after five years, and it has taken on a new dimension with Trump's involvement in 2025.

At this stage, it appears that Turkey is acting in accordance with the current situation, adopting a win-win approach. However, given the rapid changes in regional and global politics, it is clear that the region's geopolitical realities will always be at the forefront. In particular, it seems unlikely that any steps or initiatives that run counter to Turkey's interests, as a prominent regional power that shares a border with Nakhchivan, will be sustainable in the region. Undoubtedly, time will tell how the process unfolds and develops from the perspective of the existing Trump Route. However, hegemonic powers in global politics use concepts such as human rights, democracy, and national welfare as a smokescreen and act in their own states' interests.

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